

Osseointegration and advances in implant materials

Dr.Savitha P N¹,Dr.Sushma J²,Dr.Anju D³

1. Reader ,Oxford dental college and hospital
2. Assistant professor,Rajarajeshwari Dental college and Hospital
3. House surgeon,Rajarajeshwari dental college and Hospital

Received: Mar 10, 2026

Accepted: Mar 31, 2026

Published: Mar 31, 2026

Abstract:- This review article is about the process of osseointegration and the evolution of dental implant materials. This helps in improving the practical skills and different treatment options in clinical practice. It mainly focuses on the mechanism of osseointegration with its improved techniques and the evolution of implant materials from basic material to other materials which are more biologically stable. One of the most basic material used for implant prosthesis is the titanium based material due to its superior biological and mechanical properties. A successful implant treatment has become a permanent solution for patients with one or more missing natural teeth as it builds up their confidence and oral health. Hence, osseointegration and the type of implant material used plays a major role for the success rate. This review also discusses about different types of materials based on their properties and finally the future aspects of the improved techniques and materials used for implant prosthesis.

Introduction:-

Dental implants are used to replace the natural teeth roots to restore their appearance and function .These are placed within the jaw bone where a process called ‘Osseointegration’ occurs. It is a natural process where the bone grows around the implant surface in order to create a direct connection between the bone and the implant which is required for their stability, firmness and ever lasting prosthesis. Initially osseointegration was experimented in 1950s by implanting titanium screws into rabbit bones and completely incorporating them to the extent that their removal was only accomplished by fracture. The main factors affecting osseointegration are related to the implant design, composition, surface topography, bone matrix etc. Biologically this process of osseointegration closely resembles the process of fracture healing¹.

Per-Ingvar Branemark coined the term ‘osseointegration’ in 1980s, which was originally defined as as ‘a direct structural and functional connection between ordered, living bone and the surface of a load - carrying implant’. Later a more clinical definition was devised as a process in which the rigid fixation of alloplastic materials is achieved and maintained in bone during functional loading ².The clinical success of implant is fundamentally attributed to the process of osseointegration where titanium and zirconia directly integrate with the bone tissue to provide a long-term stability and survival rate. Branemark’s accomplishment of placing a titanium implant ,which was functional for more than four decades was a turning point in dentistry that resulted in the guiding principles of implant practice ³. Stability of dental implants plays a critical role in the process of osseointegration⁴.

There are different types of materials used to manufacture the implant and its related components. Initially the implant treatment procedure were performed in two surgical phases with the duration of 3-6 months. Currently it is possible to insert and load an implant during the same surgical procedure, due to several factors such as improved quality of implants, surface modifications, improved surgical technique, etc². Implant surfaces with certain properties like hydrophilicity, multifunctional coatings and incorporated drug systems have become the favourable outcomes for improved osseointegration. Surface modification of dental implants is crucial for osseointegration and also the reduction of early implant failures⁵. The antimicrobial materials have been evolved for the prevention and treatment of orthopedic implant associated infections and for the controlled release of antimicrobial agents⁶.

Osseointegration:-

As the word describes ‘osseo’ means ‘bone’ and ‘integration’ means ‘to fuse’.

Histologically it has been observed that osseointegration is an indicative factor of lack of any biological reaction on the surface by which the implant comes into contact¹. The process of osseointegration depends on both the cells and the surface of the implant body, the surface of the implant should adhere the cells by allowing specific proteins to be adsorbed, that triggers the mechanisms of osseointegration².

Another theory was put forth based on the bone-implant interface, which was termed as 'fibro-osseointegration'. American Academy of Implant Dentistry defined it as 'tissue to implant contact with healthy dense collagenous tissue in between the implant and bone'. This theory is no more accepted as there are no collagen fibers present between the bones and implant, hence remodeling cannot be possible in fibro-osseointegration⁷.

Process of osseointegration:-

The basic steps involved in the process of osseointegration;

- i. Many experimental studies have been shown that bone and bone derived cells form bone or bone-like tissue on the implant surfaces⁸.
- ii. The formation of bone at the implant surface is dependent on the cellular interactions at the interface⁸.
- iii. The initial stage involves platelets and immune cells (macrophages) which contribute to the release of osteoprogenitor cells⁸.
- iv. These osteoprogenitor cells later differentiate to osteoblasts, which is an essential step in assuring the bone formation⁸.

Osseointegration is a series of complex physiological mechanisms similar to those occurring in the healing process of fracture. The initial new bone formation may be found on implant surface around 1 week post-implantation, and bone remodeling begins in between 6 and 12 weeks which continues further. Osseointegration in areas with bone resorption can be enhanced by using bone replacement materials in immediate implant procedures consecutively with guided bone regeneration techniques⁹.

Macrophages do not promote osseointegration only by immunomodulation, but also they secrete a variety of cytokines, which play a major role in the angiogenic and cytogenetic phases of osseointegration¹⁰. Branemark, in one of the studies on microcirculation, has observed the bone tissue growing into narrow spaces in titanium and titanium chambers that gets incorporated in the bone tissue firmly. When the implant is placed in the bone, intercellular matrix proteins are derived from the interstitial fluid and blood which forms a protein layer on the implant surface. Through this protein layer cell adhesion, migration, and differentiation are initiated, which helps in an interaction of cells with the implant surface¹¹. The process of osseointegration was lower in grafted areas with HA/TCP when compared to that seen in native bone areas due to their reduced biological properties for bone formation¹².

Requirements of osseointegration:-

There are various factors affecting the implant stability such as - surgical procedures, postoperative care, medications, implant material, etc. Implant failure occurs when the tissue fails to achieve osseointegration with the dental implant, resulting in early or late implant loss. Early implant loss occurs due to lack of adequate osseointegration, while late failures is due to the loss of an already integrated implant due to occlusal overloading or peri-implantitis¹³.

Factors for effective osseointegration⁷:-

- ✓ Implant biocompatibility
- ✓ Implant design

- ✓ Implant surface
- ✓ Surgical considerations
- ✓ Condition of host tissue
- ✓ Loading conditions⁷
- ✓ Quality of bone¹⁴

Osseointegration is a measure of implant stability, which occurs in two stages- primary and secondary. The primary stability of an implant comes from mechanical engagement with compact bone, while the secondary stability provides biological stability through bone regeneration and remodeling. It is a measure of clinical immobility of an implant¹⁴.

Various factors causing the implant failure are;

Systemic conditions such as,

- ✓ Diabetes
- ✓ Smoking
- ✓ Certain medications¹⁴
- ✓ Osteoporosis

But, literature has proven inconsistent relationships between implant failures and these conditions like controlled diabetes, moderate smoking, and use of certain medications¹⁴.

Certain medications including proton pump inhibitors, NSAIDs, selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), glucocorticoids and bisphosphonates are associated with the implant failure rates¹⁴.

And there is no direct evidence that patients with HIV, cardiovascular disease, neurologic disorders, hypothyroidism, etc have a decreased rate of implant osseointegration¹⁵.

Local factors include,

- ✓ Surgical technique
- ✓ Implant site
- ✓ prosthetic considerations
- ✓ Improper implant placement
- ✓ Poor bone quality
- ✓ Previous surgeries like bone grafts / sinus lifts¹⁴.

Some conditions like osteoporosis and bone malignancies can cause osteonecrosis of the jaws¹⁵.

Few other properties of the implant that influences the rate of osseointegration are, surface energy, chemical potential, strain hardening, the presence of impurities, material thickness, and the presence of metal and non-metal composites, which affects the bone tissue reactions².

Implant materials:-

There are different success rate of implants among different dental implant systems. Commercially pure ‘titanium’ is the prime material of choice being used. But there is no exact explanation of the difference between success or failure among different implant materials².

Earlier, machined dental implants were being used which were introduced by Branemark, which were being manufactured, submitted for cleaning, decontamination and sterilization. The main advantage of these machined implants is their surfaces have grooves, ridges and marks of the tools used in manufacturing, these surface defects provide mechanical resistance through bone interlocking. But the morphology of these implants is such that, they require a longer time duration between surgery and implant loading².

Titanium and titanium alloys have high success rate due to their properties such as biocompatibility, high corrosion resistance and their capacity for bone integration. But these implants do not provide anti-infection property. Various methods are tried to improve the antimicrobial properties of dental implants¹⁶. The mechanical properties of titanium are superior to those of zirconia, with improved osseointegration without any surface treatment . Zirconia is superior to titanium in inhibiting bacterial adhesion , hence more suitable for abutments¹⁷.

Types of implant materials:-

- ✓ Metals Eg- Titanium
- ✓ Ceramics - Zirconia
- ✓ Polymers - Polyethylene
- ✓ Composites - Combination of polymer and ceramic.

Ceramic implants:-

Ceramics and polymers offer good biocompatibility, esthetics and resistance to corrosion when compared to metallic materials. Polymers also provide high flexibility and wear resistance.

Ceramics are replacing metallic implants due to their better properties and lack of metal allergy.

Clinical data suggests that hydroxyapatite- coated dental implants may be used in fresh extraction sites, with short implants, grafted maxillary/nasal sinuses¹⁸.

From a biological point of view, zirconia has a low affinity to bacterial plaque, good soft tissue integration and low inflammatory infiltrate, which may lower the risk of peri- implant diseases¹⁹.

Advancement in implant materials:-

One of the most commonly used advanced material is zirconia [ceramic], after titanium.

Implant systems have progressed from traditional titanium to many biocompatible alternative materials such as zirconia, titanium-zirconium alloys, enabling enhanced integration and durability³. The computer-aided designing and manufacturing (CAD/CAM) system and CBCT have improved the diagnostic precision, implant planning, accuracy and reduced time duration and postoperative complications³. In dentistry, esthetics have become a predominant factor among the individuals, therefore metal-free treatment is now popular. Though its mechanical properties are insufficient, their esthetics are preferred. We can scientifically compare the properties of both titanium and zirconia, but still the best among them as an implant material is not being judged¹⁷.

Properties of zirconia as an ideal dental implant:-

- a) Biocompatibility
- b) Osseointegration
- c) Esthetics
- d) Limit peri-implantitis
- e) Reduce plaque formation
- f) Good healing and soft-tissue adhesion¹⁷

But both titanium and zirconia have their own advantages and disadvantages, there is no material without any disadvantage. Zirconia is brittle and has less corrosion resistance when compared to titanium. So, the material to be chosen purely depends on the patient’s age, oral health conditions and their preference.

Titanium alloys:-

Research has aimed to develop alloying techniques for titanium to optimize biocompatibility and mechanical properties. Titanium implants cannot be placed in narrow bones such as in anterior alveolar ridge, that also causes bone loss. Thus different titanium alloys are developed for improving the mechanical strength for small-diameter implants²⁰.

Titanium-6aluminium-4vanadium (Ti-6Al-4V) is one of the commonly used titanium alloys²⁰.

Titanium-zirconium alloy provides various properties like ,the oxides on this alloy surfaces are more stable, offers favourable corrosion resistance and improved strength especially for small-diameter implants. It also showed fewer structural changes during sand blasting and they are well suited for implantation in cortical bone.

But zirconia can also influence the corrosion resistance of titanium alloys²⁰.

Polymers:-

In case of atrophic alveolar ridges, guided bone regeneration (GBR) and guided tissue regeneration (GTR) are the most commonly used techniques for increasing the bone volume. These techniques require the placement of certain barrier membranes, which is the important element for bone growth. So, there are latest advances in polymeric material membranes of synthetic origin which are currently being used²¹. Guided bone regeneration promotes the bone neof ormation in bone defects through osteogenesis, osteoconduction and osteoinduction, to restore the structural and functional characteristics of bone tissue. Barrier membrane requires about 4-6 weeks for tissue regeneration and 16-24 weeks for bone regeneration²¹.

Resorbable membranes, composed of either natural or synthetic polymers are most commonly used in GBR²¹.

CAD/CAM system implants:-

CAD/CAM systems provide advanced precision and accuracy in present day implantology. It brings about revolutionary changes in implant planning and fabrication that brings about enhanced mechanical interlocking and long-term stability³. It improves the prosthetic fit and reduces the treatment time. But it requires a high cost digital equipments and well-trained personnel, that limits its accessibility³.

But a major disadvantage of these implants is the implant-abutment microleakage. It depends on the material type and the fabrication technique²². After various analysis, it showed that ZrCAD (Zirconia) and Co-CrMill (cobalt-chromium) has the most favourable microleakage when compared to Co-CrLS (cobalt-chromium laser-sintered)²².

Nanotechnology:-

Nanotechnology overcomes various properties of implants such as, bone integration, resist infection and long term stability. It works by modifying the materials at a microscopic level to improve the process of osseointegration. It plays an important role in 'nanotopography' modifications. These are described in terms of both nanoroughness and nanofeatures². The surface roughness of the implant material can be modified by adding nanofeatures². Acid-etching is one of the method used in microtopography and the nanofabricated samples with well-defined dimensions aim in modulating cell activity².

The benefits of adding nanoparticles are⁵,

- ✓ It resists the bacterial contamination.
- ✓ Promotes faster healing period.
- ✓ Early implant loading.

- ✓ Increases surface interaction with cells and proteins.
- ✓ Benefits the sites with poor bone quality.
- ✓ Reduces the implant failure.

Different nano/micro structures are accompanied by different levels of roughness. Nanostructured surfaces like nanogrooves, nanopillars, etc have good antimicrobial property¹⁶.

Antibacterial/antimicrobial surface materials:-

Similar to periodontal diseases, peri-implant diseases are commonly occurring due to the plaque formation on dental implants¹⁶. The most common among them is peri-implantitis due to bacterial invasion, which has led to the development of different antibacterial strategies for implant materials¹⁶. Titanium implants which are widely used do not have an effective anti-infection ability. Therefore many researchers have tried to improve the antibacterial properties of implants in various ways¹⁶.

The different methods are¹⁶;

- ✓ Antiadhesion by micro/nanostructures
- ✓ Contact killing by AMPs (Antimicrobial peptides)
- ✓ Release killing by drug release coatings
- ✓ Intrinsic antibacterial materials

Modifications of implant surface:-

Several methods have been proposed to modify the implant surfaces to improve the success rate of implants². As different cells and proteins interact with the implant surface, the analysis of different properties of implant surface is important². It involves the surface roughness, surface energy, chemical composition, chemical potential, etc. The surface roughness is assessed at three scales: macroscopically, microscopically and nanoscopically². Each type of roughness determines different contacts with the cells².

Besides the surface topography, chemical composition of the surface has an influence on the secondary stability of the implant². Hence, the morphology of implant surfaces can be modified by chemical, mechanical, electrochemical and laser beam treatments².

Some of the advantages of treating the implant surface are²;

- ✓ Reduce the loading time after surgery
- ✓ Accelerate bone growth and maturation
- ✓ improve the implant stability
- ✓ Increase implant surface area
- ✓ Modify wettability
- ✓ Improve osseointegration

Surface modifications can be divided as;

- a) Machined implants
- b) Plasma spray
- c) Laser etching
- d) Acid etching
- e) Anodizing
- f) Biomimetic coatings²
- g) Texturization
- h) Hydrophilization
- i) Coatings
- j) Nano/microparticles⁵

They are broadly categorized into, physical, chemical and biochemical alterations²⁴.

- ✓ Physical modifications include changes in surface topography and roughness.
- ✓ Chemical modifications involve the alteration of surface chemistry.

- ✓ Biochemical modifications include the incorporation of bioactive molecules such as growth factors, peptides and proteins²⁴.

Chemicals used for coated surfaces are calcium, phosphate and hydroxyapatite due to their biocompatibility and good outcomes throughout and beyond the osseointegration⁵. These can change the properties of biocompatibility, corrosion resistance and mechanical features of the implant surface⁵.

Plasma spray creates texturized coatings that leads to higher cell adhesion and proliferation that improves the bone quality⁵. Hydroxyapatite (a layer of calcium and phosphate atoms) is used as a coating on the implant surface through plasma spraying technique²³.

Nanotechnology opened a new era by introducing new nanostructured materials and coatings. Nanostructured surfaces have an impact on both direct and indirect cell interactions guiding in specific molecular events²³. The cell adhesion and motility were found to be altered with nano-treated surfaces, whereas bacterial adhesion and colonization were decreased²³. Nanoroughness provides ample binding sites for increased cell attachment and a more stable mechanical interlocking with native bone leading to faster osseointegration²³. Titania nanotubes, chitosan and nanohydroxyapatite coatings are the nanomaterials that have been explored for enhanced osseointegration²³.

Most of the implant surfaces have been analyzed by in vitro and in vivo studies, showing high clinical success rates. Further research and studies are required to improve and describe the interaction between cells and implant surfaces.

Future outlook:-

The field of implant dentistry is fastly developing, with the use of new technologies, AI, research, all designed to enhance the clinical performance and treatment³. There are various advanced materials and different techniques that have been implemented for use in implant dentistry. But still many studies are on going and are required in the implementation of new materials for improving the process of osseointegration. These advancements in dental implantology has improved the implant success and longevity³. The intervening years have seen different advances in technology transforming the discipline, like CAD/CAM, AI and robotics which have improved the benefits of dental implants³.

Material development is also promoting the implant success at present. Titanium is still the gold standard implant material being used because of its excellent mechanical and biological properties³. Further the advances in antimicrobial coatings, bioactive surfaces, regenerative methods have the ability to counteract the risks of bacterial infections like peri-implantitis in future³. Present day implantology receives precised materials from CAD/CAM systems which produce personalized implants according to each patient's needs³. The development of biosensor implanted devices is still in progress, for the early diagnosis of peri implant complications³.

Some other technologies such as regenerative materials and AI infrastructure are not being accessible for underserved populations, because of their expense³. In the future, a synergetic equilibrium between technology advancement, patient safety and environmental sustainability will be necessary in order to achieve successful implant innovation³.

Conclusion:-

As described earlier, dental implants are the long-term solution for the replacement of missing teeth, with their success dependent on effective osseointegration. For patients with compromised bone conditions, modern techniques have been developed for better osseointegration and to enhance the clinical outcomes. Although, implant treatment requires a high cost and increased time duration, it is a reliable option for patients with missing teeth and good bone quality, as it gives a permanent solution.

Osseointegration, being an important process for the long-term stability of implants, should be achieved effectively. And there are many advances in the techniques and implant materials in order to enhance osseointegration and many other properties. But, still there are studies that are on going to prove these materials and techniques in terms of long-term clinical basis, to apply them successfully. Implantology has brought about

various methods to provide long term satisfaction to the patients and also there are many advanced methods which are being established in day to day life.

The knowledge about the process of osseointegration and the different types of materials with the advances is necessary to achieve a successful implant therapy. To conclude, implant therapy has become and also becoming the best treatment option for patients requiring fixed dental prosthesis. And every dentists must apply this knowledge and provide satisfactory treatment for all the patients.

References:-

- (1).Zidrou C, Kapetanou A, Rizou S. The effect of drugs on implant osseointegration-A narrative review. *Injury*. 2023 Aug 1;54(8):110888.
- (2) Elias CN, Meirelles L. Improving osseointegration of dental implants. *Expert review of medical devices*. 2010 Mar 1;7(2):241-56
- (3) .James JR, Kharat A, Chinnakutti S, Kamble S, Mandal M, Das A. The future of dental implants: A narrative review of trends, technologies, and patient considerations. *Cureus*. 2025 Aug 18;17(8)
- (4) .Lioubavina-Hack N, Lang NP, Karring T. Significance of primary stability for osseointegration of dental implants. *Clinical oral implants research*. 2006 Jun;17(3):244-50
- (5) .Kunrath MF, Garaicoa-Pazmino C, Giraldo-Osorno PM, Haj Mustafa A, Dahlin C, Larsson L, Asa'ad F. Implant surface modifications and their impact on osseointegration and peri-implant diseases through epigenetic changes: a scoping review. *Journal of periodontal research*. 2024 Dec;59(6):1095-114
- (6) .Cyphert EL, Zhang N, Learn GD, Hernandez CJ, von Recum HA. Recent advances in the evaluation of antimicrobial materials for resolution of orthopedic implant-associated infections in vivo. *ACS infectious diseases*. 2021 Nov 11;7(12):3125-60
- (7) .Nandal S, Ghalaut P, Shekhawat H, Nagar P. Osseointegration in dental implants: a literature review. *Med. Sci*. 2014;4:411-3.
- (8) .Cooper LF, Shirazi S. Osseointegration—the biological reality of successful dental implant therapy: a narrative review. *Frontiers of Oral and Maxillofacial Medicine*. 2022 Dec 30;4.
- (9) .OSSEOINTEGRATION OF DENTAL IMPLANTS: A REVIEW Forna Norinal * 1 —Gr.T.Popal University of Medicine and Pharmacy Iasi, Romania, Faculty of Dental Medicine correspondent member of AOSR; full member of ASM
- (10) .Fang X, Sun D, Li Y, Han X, Gan Y, Jiao J, Jiang M, Gong H, Qi Y, Zhao J. Macrophages in the process of osseointegration around the implant and their regulatory strategies. *Connective Tissue Research*. 2024 Jan 2;65(1):1-5.
- (11) .Pandey C, Rokaya D, Bhattarai BP. Contemporary concepts in osseointegration of dental implants: a review. *BioMed research international*. 2022;2022(1):6170452.
- (12) .Lima JR, Soares PB, Pinotti FE, Marcantonio RA, Marcantonio-Junior E, de Oliveira GJ. Comparison of the osseointegration of implants placed in areas grafted with HA/TCP and native bone. *Microscopy Research and Technique*. 2022 Aug;85(8):2776-83.
- (13) .AlRowis R, Albelaihi F, Alquraini H, Almojel S, Alsudais A, Alaqeely R. Factors affecting dental implant failure: A retrospective analysis. *InHealthcare* 2025 Jun 6 (Vol. 13, No. 12, p. 1356). MDPI
- (14) .Parithimarkalaignan S, Padmanabhan TV. Osseointegration: an update. *The Journal of Indian Prosthodontic Society*. 2013 Mar;13(1):2-6.

- (15) .Aghaloo T, Pi-Anfruns J, Moshaverinia A, Sim D, Grogan T, Hadaya D. The Effects of Systemic Diseases and Medications on Implant Osseointegration: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Oral & Maxillofacial Implants*. 2019 Jan 2;34
- (16) .Chen Z, Wang Z, Qiu W, Fang F. Overview of antibacterial strategies of dental implant materials for the prevention of peri-implantitis. *Bioconjugate Chemistry*. 2021 Mar 29;32(4):627-38
- (17) .Hanawa T. Zirconia versus titanium in dentistry: A review. *Dental Materials Journal*. 2020 Jan 30;39(1):24-36
- (18) .Meffert RM. Ceramic-coated implant systems. *Advances in Dental Research*. 1999 Jun;13(1):170-2.
- (19).Schnurr E, Sperlich M, Sones A, Romanos GE, Rutkowski JL, Duddeck DU, Neugebauer J, Att W, Sperlich M, Volz KU, Ghanaati S. Ceramic implant rehabilitation: consensus statements from joint congress for ceramic implantology: consensus statements on ceramic implant. *Journal of Oral Implantology*. 2024 Aug 1;50(4):435-45
- (20).Haugen HJ, Chen H. Is there a better biomaterial for dental implants than titanium?—a review and meta-study analysis. *Journal of Functional Biomaterials*. 2022 Apr 20;13(2):46.
- (21) .Lima-Sánchez B, Baus-Domínguez M, Serrera-Figallo MA, Torres-Lagares D. Advances in synthetic polymer membranes for guided bone regeneration in dental implants: A scoping review. *Journal of functional biomaterials*. 2025 Apr 22;16(5):149
- (22) .molinero-Mourelle P, Rocuzzo A, Yilmaz B, Lam WY, Pow EH, Highsmith JD, Gómez-Polo M. Microleakage assessment of CAD-CAM Cobalt-Chrome and Zirconia abutments on a conical connection dental implant: A comparative in vitro study. *Clinical oral implants research*. 2022 Sep;33(9):945-52
- (23) .Marasli C, Katifelis H, Gazouli M, Lagopati N. Nano-based approaches in surface modifications of dental implants: a literature review. *Molecules*. 2024 Jun 27;29(13):3061
- (24).Shayeb MA, Elfadil S, Abutayyem H, Shqaidef A, Marrapodi MM, Cicciù M, Minervini G. Bioactive surface modifications on dental implants: a systematic review and meta-analysis of osseointegration and longevity. *Clinical oral investigations*. 2024 Oct 11;28(11):592